

**LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES AND LEVEL OF MOTIVATION OF
EDUCATION STUDENTS OF ISABELA STATE UNIVERSITY-ECHAGUE**

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Abstract

This study explored the language learning strategies (LLS) and motivational levels of students learning English, examining variations by sex and the relationship between strategy use and motivation. The respondent pool consisted predominantly of female students. Findings revealed that students moderately engaged with a range of LLS, with metacognitive strategies being the most frequently employed suggesting increased learner autonomy and self-regulation. Social and cognitive strategies followed, indicating the value placed on interaction and active language use. and compensation strategies were the least used, suggesting a move away from rote methods.

Motivational levels were generally high, driven by the desire to learn English. Male students reported significantly higher use of cognitive and social strategies than female students, reflecting more proactive engagement. Motivation levels, however, were statistically similar across sexes, except in one item where male students favored more English courses.

Importantly, a significant positive correlation was found between all five LLS and motivation, reinforcing motivation as a key factor in strategic language learning. These findings support the growing emphasis on learner-centered instruction and the role of motivation in enhancing metacognitive awareness and behavioral engagement.

It is recommended that educators adopt engaging, strategy-based, and motivationally supportive teaching approaches to further enhance students' language learning outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

The important role of the English language continually grows as the world experiences the period of globalization, wherein it becomes the Lingua Franca of almost the globe because of its usage and domination in the fields of education, business, communication, and other aspects. As stated by Crystal (n.d.) as cited by Oda (2011) and Quibilan (2017), 90 percent of published articles were written in English as a medium and 85 percent of the international

organizations in the world including the United Nations (UN) have English as their official or part of their official language/s.

Hence, learning the language, especially in educational institutions, is very important to become globally competitive as the world is in the current context of globalization. Wherein in this context, students can only be globally competent if they can communicate effectively with diverse audiences (Asia Society, 2005), which means that they can use the lingua franca effectively in expressing their ideas and knowledge in international settings.

As the necessity to learn the English language from the international perspective arises, the strategies on how to effectively learn it are indeed vital, especially on the part of the students. Having strategies to effectively learn the language will enable the students to become good communicators of it, thus, helping them to become proficient and globally competent in using it both in academic and professional realms. Their proficiency will help them attain power and progress as this language serves as a tool for learning and a medium of communication in wider perspectives and aspects (Batang and Maramag, 2018).

In relation to this, the employment of specific strategies is important like the LLS, which can assist the students to effectively learn the language. LLS as stated by Oxford (1990) are "operations employed by the learner to aid the acquisition, storage, retrieval, and use of information, (they are) specific actions taken by the learner to make learning easier, faster, more enjoyable, more self-directed, more effective, and more transferable to new situations". As examined from its definition, the effective aspect is also part of it, which means that in learning a particular language, motivation is also important. As in the experience of the researchers, learning the English language depends also on the motivation of the learners. The emotional state may determine if the student is prepared or not in learning the input of the language. However, the researchers are unaware of the motivation that may help to determine the specific LLS to be used in effectively learning the language. Even though according to the study of Oxford and Nyikos (1989) and as cited by Rahimi et. al (2004) about the effect of the number of factors on strategy use, including motivation, they found that motivation is the single most important factor that influences the LLS usage. However, this does not reveal what were the strategies used by learners who have a high or low motivation level.

In connection to this, several variables were also determined in relation to the use of these strategies which include age, sex, and experience in studying as cited by Khamkien (2010) based on the previous study by Dornyei (2001). When pertaining to sex as a variable in language learning strategy, based on the citation of Khamkien (2010), it showed that female learners used more learning strategies than their male counterparts and females used the affective and compensation strategies more than male ones. In terms of age, according to Ellis (1994), it is considered a clear factor in the use of learning strategies by the learners. He explained that younger learners tend to use simple strategies while older adults are more inclined to use complex strategies.

Several studies explored the nature and factors that affect the usage of the LLS however, they are mostly from foreign sources and publications. Hence, the researchers conducted this research study to help explore this topic, add to the existing body of knowledge and literature in the local context, and see the findings that are applicable in the local setting. Particularly, it sought to: determine the profile variables of the students; their level of

motivation in learning the English language; find out if there is a significant difference in the LLS employment when grouped according to their profile; if there is a significant difference in their level of motivation when grouped according to their profile; and determine if there is a significant relationship between LLS and level of motivation. Furthermore, it aimed to determine if the above-mentioned results can be validated in the local setting given that these can vary because of the variation in the background of the respondents.

This study was conducted at Isabela State University-Echague, particularly at the College of Education during the A.Y. 2021-2022 and this was only limited in determining the relationship between the LLS usage of the respondents and their level of motivation.

METHODS

Research Design

This research study is quantitative research because it dealt mainly with data that can be quantified and it further employed descriptive-correlational research design since the main aim of this study is to describe the possible relationship that exists between the major variables, particularly between the LLS and academic performance of the students, the level of motivation and their academic performance, and the LLS and their level of motivation.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

313 respondents are being selected from all the year levels and courses of the college through the employment of a stratified sampling procedure and computed through Slovin's Formula. The total sample size was divided into strata thereby obtaining the total number of respondents in each stratum and represented in the following: Bachelor of Secondary Education had 129 respondents; Bachelor of Elementary Education had 76 respondents; Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education had 55 respondents; and Bachelor of Physical Education had 53 respondents.

Research Instrument

The data needed were elicited using the 50-item Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) developed by Rebecca Oxford in 1989 to determine the LLS employed by the students. For their level of motivation, the Motivation Questionnaire (36 items) adopted from Salimi (2000) as cited by Rahimi et al. (2004) was used. The survey questionnaires, both with five-point Likert Scale measurement, were administered through the Google Form.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

At the onset, the data were gathered upon the approval of the request letter of the Dean with the attached data gathering consent form for the respondents. The data collected was organized through the coding process before proceeding to the statistical treatment wherein frequency counts and percentages were used for the profile variables of the respondents. Mean computation was utilized for the frequency of LLS employment and their level of motivation. A T-test was employed in testing the significant difference between the LLS usage and their level of motivation when they were grouped based on their profile variables. For the significant relationship between the LLS and academic performance, level of motivation and academic performance, and LLS and level of motivation, Pearson R was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex. The table reveals that in terms of sex, the respondent pool was predominantly female, comprising 236 individuals, while male respondents numbered 77.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency (n=313)	Percent
Sex		
Male	77	24.60
Female	236	75.40

Language Learning Strategies

Table 2 presents the mean scores of language learning strategies employed by the respondents, summarized across six major categories. The Grand Mean of 3.41 indicates that, overall, students sometimes use these strategies, reflecting a moderate frequency of engagement with language learning techniques.

Table 2. Language Learning Strategies Employed by the Respondents

Strategies	Mean	Description
1. Remembering more effectively (Memory Strategy)	3.32	Sometimes used
2. Using all your mental processes (Cognitive strategy)	3.40	Sometimes used
3. Compensating for Missing Knowledge	3.24	Sometimes used
4. Organizing and evaluating your learning (Metacognitive strategy)	3.60	Usually used
5. Managing your emotions (Affective strategy)	3.40	Sometimes used
6. Learning with others (Social strategy)	3.44	Sometimes used
Grand Mean	3.41	Sometimes used

Table 2 provides the language learning strategies employed by the respondents.

Among the strategies, metacognitive strategies recorded the highest usage ($M = 3.60$), categorized as usually used. This suggests that students are increasingly taking control of their own learning processes by setting goals, organizing tasks, and monitoring their progress in learning English. The relatively frequent use of metacognitive strategies may reflect the influence of current educational approaches that promote learner autonomy, self-reflection, and strategic thinking as essential components of language development.

Social strategies were next in frequency ($M = 3.44$), indicating that learners often rely on interpersonal communication to enhance their understanding. Asking for help, seeking clarification, and interacting with proficient English users are examples of these strategies, which support the communicative and collaborative aspects of language learning.

Cognitive and affective strategies both received mean scores of 3.40, denoting moderate use. Cognitive strategies include activities like analyzing, practicing, or using media to enhance learning, indicating that students are actively engaging with language materials, albeit inconsistently. Affective strategies, on the other hand, help students manage their emotions and motivation—such as reducing anxiety or encouraging themselves to speak English despite fear of errors. The moderate use of these strategies suggests that while emotional and psychological factors are considered in learning, they may still pose challenges for some students.

Memory strategies (M = 3.32) and compensation strategies (M = 3.24) were the least used, though still within the sometimes used category. This may indicate that students are less inclined to use rote memorization or to develop ways to compensate for unknown vocabulary or grammar structures. These findings may reflect a shift away from traditional memorization-based learning toward more strategic, communicative, and critical approaches.

Overall, while students employ a diverse range of language learning strategies, the majority are used only moderately. The strong showing of metacognitive strategies may signal the impact of evolving instructional priorities that emphasize self-directed and higher-order thinking skills. These results align with the findings of Thongma et al. (2013), who similarly reported medium-frequency use of English learning strategies among students. Their study attributed this pattern to the ongoing educational shift from rote learning to strategies that foster deeper engagement and critical language use.

Level of Motivation in Learning English Language

Table 3. Level of Motivation in Learning English Language

Indicators	Mean	Description	Interpretation
1. I like English subject	3.93	Agree	Highly Motivated
2. I would like to have more personal practice in the English course.	3.95	Agree	Highly Motivated
3. If I saw a tourist on the street, I would like to speak English.	3.68	Agree	Highly Motivated
4. I would like to have more English spoken.	4.04	Agree	Highly Motivated
5. In my English study, I get through hard work.	3.88	Agree	Highly Motivated
6. Doing my homework, I carry on until I really know it.	3.77	Agree	Highly Motivated
7. I work more on my English studies than other subjects.	3.36	Undecided	Fairly Motivated
8. If there is a panel discussion on the radio in English, I just try to understand it.	3.94	Agree	Highly Motivated
9. Learning English is more important just because I want to get a good job.	3.94	Agree	Highly Motivated

10. Other people think more highly of me if I know a foreign language.	3.49	Undecided	Fairly Motivated
11. Learning a foreign language makes me a more knowledgeable person.	3.69	Agree	Highly Motivated
12. I would like to learn English because I would like to teach it.	3.99	Agree	Highly Motivated
13. Learning English is important because I can then get in contact with English-speaking people.	4.12	Agree	Highly Motivated
14. I would like to learn English because I would like to be an active speaker.	4.10	Agree	Highly Motivated
15. I learn English because I would like to join the English people.	4.12	Agree	Highly Motivated
16. I learn English because I would like to get familiar with English culture.	4.12	Agree	Highly Motivated
17. I would like to learn English perfectly.	4.03	Agree	Highly Motivated
18. I am curious about it.	4.04	Agree	Highly Motivated
19. I would like to learn English even if it weren't compulsory.	3.97	Agree	Highly Motivated
20. I feel learning a foreign language truly helps me to develop my real self.	3.95	Agree	Highly Motivated
21. I think academic learning is pleasant.	4.12	Agree	Highly Motivated
22. I think that the number of academic years should be increased.	3.42	Undecided	Fairly Motivated
23. If I could choose, I would take more courses in English.	3.92	Agree	Highly Motivated
24. I think English courses in university should be increased.	3.96	Agree	Highly Motivated
25. I love English/American music.	4.20	Agree	Highly Motivated
26. It is important to know life in the English-speaking world.	3.95	Agree	Highly Motivated
27. I found the English way of life exciting.	4.12	Agree	Highly Motivated
28. I believe one should know English history and culture.	3.92	Agree	Highly Motivated
29. I like the sound of English.	4.07	Agree	Highly Motivated
30. I think English is an exciting language.	4.06	Agree	Highly Motivated
31. I think it's useful to know the inner structure of English.	3.69	Agree	Highly Motivated
32. I would really like to know how the English language works.	4.09	Agree	Highly Motivated
33. I love the way English is taught to us.	3.98	Agree	Highly Motivated

34. I feel I can express myself in the English lessons.	3.85	Agree	Highly Motivated
35. I find our English teaching methods good.	3.93	Agree	Highly Motivated
GRAND MEAN	3.88	AGREE	HIGHLY MOTIVATED

In alignment with the data presented in Table 4, the findings suggest that students are generally highly motivated to learn the English language. This is evident in their strong desire to master English (M = 4.14) and to emulate active, fluent speakers (M = 4.10). These results indicate that students recognize the crucial role of English in effective communication, particularly within academic settings where English is predominantly used as the medium of instruction across various subjects.

However, the data also reveals areas of concern regarding instructional approaches. Students reported only moderate motivation when English teaching methods are perceived as boring (M = 3.15), suggesting that uninspiring or monotonous pedagogy can hinder their engagement and overall learning outcomes. Additionally, their motivation to prioritize English over other subjects was also moderate (M = 3.36), implying that, while they value English, it may not always take precedence in their academic focus.

Despite these variations, the overall general mean (GM = 3.88) reflects a high level of motivation among students to learn English. This suggests that, collectively, the students exhibit a strong intrinsic desire and put forth effort to acquire the language, driven by their recognition of its academic and practical value. These findings are supported by Indriani (2020), who emphasizes that motivated language learners are characterized by their eagerness, sustained effort, and consistent participation in learning activities.

Difference in Language Learning Strategies in terms of Sex

Table 4 presents the differences in the use of language learning strategies (LLS) among students when grouped according to sex. While most strategies showed no statistically significant difference between male and female respondents, notable exceptions emerged in the cognitive and social strategy categories.

Table 4. Difference in Language Learning Strategies in terms of Sex

Language Learning Strategies	Group Means		t-value	p-value
	Male	Female		
1. Remembering more effectively (Memory Strategy)	3.56	3.49	0.65 ^{ns}	0.52
2. Using all your mental processes (Cognitive strategy)	3.47	3.14	2.59*	0.01
3. Compensating for Missing Knowledge	3.23	3.15	0.75 ^{ns}	0.45
4. Organizing and evaluating your learning (Metacognitive strategy)	3.55	3.51	0.30 ^{ns}	0.77
5. Managing your emotions (Affective strategy)	3.53	3.50	0.29 ^{ns}	0.77
6. Learning with others (Social strategy)	3.71	3.44	2.32*	0.02

Specifically, cognitive strategies revealed a significant difference ($t = 2.59, p = 0.01$), where male students ($M = 3.47$) reported higher usage compared to female students ($M = 3.14$). This suggests that male learners tend to engage more frequently in activities such as initiating conversations or mentally rehearsing English language use, which may reflect greater confidence or assertiveness in language application.

A significant difference was also observed in social strategies ($t = 2.32, p = 0.02$), with male students again reporting higher usage ($M = 3.71$) compared to their female counterparts ($M = 3.44$). This implies that males are more likely to interact socially in English by asking others to slow down, repeating misunderstood phrases, and seeking corrections—demonstrating a more proactive and inquiry-driven approach to language learning.

These findings are consistent with the observations of Lee (2010), who reported that male students tend to use a wider range of learning strategies than females. The higher scores for males in both cognitive and social domains suggest a tendency toward active engagement and risk-taking behaviors in second language use.

Conversely, no statistically significant differences were found in the memory, compensation, metacognitive, and affective strategies. This suggests a general uniformity in how both male and female students employ these strategies. Instructional exposure and academic expectations may standardize the use of such strategies regardless of sex.

Furthermore, the analysis revealed no significant difference in strategy use based on first language. This indicates that students apply language learning strategies similarly, regardless of their linguistic backgrounds. This supports the view that the process of learning a second language follows cognitive patterns common to learning a first language. As noted by Crowley (2014), the cognitive processes involved in acquiring L1 and L2 are fundamentally similar, whether one is learning to speak a language, ride a bike, or master a skill, the underlying mechanisms remain comparable. This reinforces the idea that the learners' strategic behaviors are not strongly influenced by their native language.

Difference in the Level of Motivation in Learning the English Language when Grouped According to Sex

The findings on the difference in motivation in learning English based on sex reveal that male and female students generally exhibit similar levels of motivation, as shown by the lack of statistically significant differences in 34 out of 35 motivational indicators in Table 5.

Table 5. Difference in the Level of Motivation in Learning the English Language when Grouped According to Sex

Indicators	Group Means		t-value	p-value
	Male	Female		
1. I like English subject	3.87	3.95	0.77 ^{ns}	0.44
2. I would like to have more personal practice in the English course.	4.06	4.09	0.28 ^{ns}	0.78
3. If I saw a tourist on the street, I would like to speak English.	3.83	3.64	1.83 ^{ns}	0.07

4. I would like to have more English spoken.	4.05	4.03	0.18 ^{ns}	0.86
5. In my English study, I get through hard work.	4.01	3.83	1.79 ^{ns}	0.07
6. Doing my homework, I carry on until I really know it.	4.13	4.02	1.22 ^{ns}	0.22
7. I work more on my English studies than other subjects.	3.44	3.34	0.87 ^{ns}	0.39
8. If there is a panel discussion on the radio in English, I just try to understand it.	4.00	3.92	0.94 ^{ns}	0.35
9. Learning English is more important just because I want to get a good job.	3.82	3.86	0.33 ^{ns}	0.74
10. Other people think more highly of me if I know a foreign language.	3.60	3.45	1.21 ^{ns}	0.23
11. Learning a foreign language makes me a more knowledgeable person.	3.70	3.68	0.17 ^{ns}	0.87
12. I would like to learn English because I would like to teach it.	3.99	3.99	0.04 ^{ns}	0.97
13. Learning English is important because I can then get in contact with English-speaking people.	4.06	4.08	0.16 ^{ns}	0.88
14. I would like to learn English because I would like to be an active speaker.	4.12	4.09	0.23 ^{ns}	0.82
15. I learn English because I would like to join the English people.	3.83	3.72	0.99 ^{ns}	0.32
16. I learn English because I would like to get familiar with English culture.	3.92	3.92	0.06 ^{ns}	0.95
17. I would like to learn English perfectly.	4.10	4.16	0.53 ^{ns}	0.60
18. I am curious about it.	3.88	4.07	1.80 ^{ns}	0.08
19. I would like to learn English even if it weren't compulsory.	3.96	3.97	0.10 ^{ns}	0.92
20. I feel learning a foreign language truly helps me to develop my real self.	3.94	3.95	0.14 ^{ns}	0.89
21. I think academic learning is pleasant.	4.16	4.11	0.55 ^{ns}	0.58
22. I think that the number of academic years should be increased.	3.52	3.39	0.93 ^{ns}	0.35
23. If I could choose, I would take more courses in English.	3.78	3.64	1.21 ^{ns}	0.23
24. I think English courses in university should be increased.	3.94	3.70	2.11*	0.04
25. I love English/American music.	3.96	3.92	0.38 ^{ns}	0.70
26. It is important to know life in the English-speaking world.	3.95	3.95	0.01 ^{ns}	0.99
27. I found the English way of life exciting.	3.81	3.88	0.75 ^{ns}	0.45
28. I believe one should know English history and culture.	3.92	3.90	0.24 ^{ns}	0.81
29. I like the sound of English.	4.05	4.07	0.19 ^{ns}	0.85
30. I think English is an exciting language.	4.06	4.06	0.10 ^{ns}	0.92
31. I think it's useful to know the inner structure of English.	3.99	4.05	0.67 ^{ns}	0.50

32. I would really like to know how the English language works.	4.08	4.09	0.12 ^{ns}	0.91
33. I love the way English is taught to us.	4.01	3.97	0.44 ^{ns}	0.66
34. I feel I can express myself in the English lessons.	3.87	3.72	1.38 ^{ns}	0.17
35. I find our English teaching methods good.	3.91	3.94	0.28 ^{ns}	0.78

The only significant result was found in Item 24 (“I think English courses in university should be increased”), where male students (M = 3.94) expressed stronger agreement than female students (M = 3.70), with a t-value of 2.11 and a p-value of 0.04 indicating a significant difference at the 0.05 level. This suggests that male students may have a greater desire for more structured English instruction within the academic setting. The rest of the items, including those related to interest, cultural engagement, and communicative willingness, did not show meaningful differences between sexes, which implies that overall motivation in learning English is not strongly influenced by sex. This supports Crowley’s (2014) view that language learning, whether first or second, involves similar cognitive processes, and aligns with Lee’s (2010) findings that while strategy use may differ, motivational levels can be equally high across genders.

Relationship Between Language Learning Strategies and Level of Motivation

Table 6. Relationship Between Language Learning Strategies and Level of Motivation

Language Learning Strategies	r-value	p-value
1. Remembering more effectively (Memory Strategy)	0.19*	0.01
2. Using all your mental processes (Cognitive strategy)	0.14*	0.01
3. Compensating for Missing Knowledge	0.09 ^{ns}	0.12
4. Organizing and evaluating your learning (Metacognitive strategy)	0.22*	0.01
5. Managing your emotions (Affective strategy)	0.23*	0.01
6. Learning with others (Social strategy)	0.18*	0.01

The data presented in Table 6 reveal that all five language learning strategies (LLS)—namely memory, cognitive, metacognitive, affective, and social strategies—demonstrate a statistically significant relationship with the respondents’ level of motivation, each marked by a p-value of 0.01. The corresponding positive correlation coefficients (ranging from 0.14 to 0.23) indicate a consistent, though modest, positive association, suggesting that as learners’ motivation increases, their use of these strategies also tends to rise. While the strength of the correlations varies slightly among the strategy types, the overall pattern underscores motivation as a key driver in the strategic approach learners adopt when engaging with English language acquisition. These findings are consistent with Rahimi et al. (2004), who observed that heightened motivation contributes to more frequent and diverse use of language learning strategies. This suggests that motivation not only energizes learners but also enhances their

metacognitive awareness and behavioral engagement in the learning process, leading to more intentional and strategic language use.

CONCLUSION

1. Students moderately used language learning strategies, with metacognitive strategies most frequently employed and compensation strategies the least, reflecting a shift toward learner autonomy and strategic engagement.
2. Students demonstrated a high level of motivation to learn English, especially due to its academic and communicative relevance.
3. Male students reported significantly higher use of cognitive and social strategies than female students, suggesting greater confidence or willingness to engage in communicative tasks.
4. No significant sex-based differences were found in memory, compensation, metacognitive, or affective strategies, implying uniformity in strategy use due to similar instructional exposure.
5. Motivation levels between male and female students were largely similar, with only one indicator showing a significant difference favoring males.
6. All five language learning strategies showed a significant positive correlation with motivation, highlighting motivation as a key driver in strategic language.

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